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**Reinterpreting Flood: Studying the Historical Implication of
Koshi Flood in Northern Bihar***

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Ved Prakash[†], N. P. Palit[‡], Sandeep Kumar Gupta[§], Suraj Prasad^{}**

ABSTRACT

Flood is one of the most significant natural hazards, and people living in flood zone always face the event of flood during monsoon in India. This paper assesses the historical impacts of Koshi flood, particularly 'The Killed' and 'The Billed', in Northern Bihar. The aftermath of severe floods in the past has been assessed with the help of quantitative methods. The study is based on the secondary database. Lack of services, fragile living, and disadvantaged groups make people vulnerable to flood in the Koshi region of Bihar. The present study also tries to analyse the geographical problem of River Koshi in the northern plain of Bihar. This study will help realistic assessment of flood impact in the region. The focus area comprises of Madhubani, Darbhanga, Supaul, Saharsa, Khagaria, Madhepura, Araria, Katihar, Purnia and Bhagalpur districts of northern Bihar.

INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of civilization, people have been locating themselves along the river banks to fulfil the purpose of cultivation on fertile or alluvium soils and flat terrain as well. They also have viable access to the water needed to survive, and use the river for transportation as well. Usually, the housing constructions were made on comparative upper land area, and the lower area was used for agriculture, and grazing or pasture activities. During floods, the lower riparian region enriched with unconsolidated sedimentary deposits (alluvium), which is very fertile in nature. So, after the flood, people get benefited in agricultural activities with this fertile alluvium soil. This means people lived in harmony with floods (Kundzewicz, 2004).

With development and advancement in science & Technology around the world, rise in population growth and dynamic changes in land-use patterns have significantly multiplied the human vulnerability to floods. Harmful impacts of floods include direct mortality and morbidity and indirect displacement and widespread damage of crops, infrastructure and property (Doocyetal. 2013; IPCC, 2007). Among the oldest and known disasters, floods have been threatening humanities for ages

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[†] PhD Research Scholar, Department of Geography, Veer Kunwar Singh University, Ara, Bihar/INDIA, ved19nov@gmail.com

[‡] Associate Professor. Maharaja College, Veer Kunwar Singh University, Ara, Bihar/INDIA, drnppalit@gmail.com

[§] Professor, Sharda University, Greater Noida/INDIA, skguptabhu@gmail.com

^{**} PhD Research Scholar, Department of Geography, Delhi School of Economics, University of Delhi, Delhi/INDIA, surajprasad27@gmail.com

(Ferreira, 2011). The major impacts of floods are Loss of life, loss of infrastructure and properties etc. In recent decades, the frequency and consequences of extreme flood events have increased rapidly worldwide. Gradual population growth, heavy rainfall in an urban area, rise in frequency of extreme events (cloud burst), Climate change and significant growth in socio-economic activities in and around flood plain. Past studies (e.g. Dixit, 2009; Sinha, 2009a,b; Sinha et al., 2013, 2014) has recognized that the problems of channel instability and flooding have been aggravated in recent past. These were largely due to several interventions for water resource development activities including the embankments on both sides of the river completed in 1955–56, and a barrage at Birpur completed in 1963 (India-WRIS, 2016). The Kosi (or, Koshi) River drains through the high mountains of China and Nepal and then debouches into the alluvial plains of lower basin of northern Bihar in India. The Koshi has been a dramatic river over the previous several decades owing to its exceptionally dynamic channels and recurrent flooding (Gole and Chitale, 1966; Wells and Dorr, 1987; Sinha and Jain, 1998; Chakraborty et al., 2010).

Flood risk may have enlarged due to dynamic changes in the land cover and land use, which augment changes of hydrological systems. Deforestation, urbanization, and decrease in wetlands lead to a reduction in the accumulation of water in the basin and add to the runoff. Rapid Urbanization has a negative implication on the risk of flood vulnerability by increasing impervious surface structures (e.g. sidewalks, roofs, roads, parking lots, etc) (Kundzewicz, 2004). Prevalent concrete or solid surface structures add to the rainwater runoff as well as to the drying the soil within the solid surface, including a decrease of groundwater reserves and climate change in the city area. These attributes cause transformation in drainage patterns and enhance the risk of local or confined flooding in cities. According to EEA (2001), every 10 years, there is a loss of around 2% of the agricultural area in European territory occurs. The vulnerability of water runoff has a direct implication on peoples' livelihoods, which leads to a rise in poverty and issues of shortage of food. Generally, the underprivileged community in a developing world are severe, affected by floods as their communities are less resilient to cope up with the situation. They have inadequate options to deal with adversity. The implication of flood is more severe in an urban area, where a very high density of population, high concentration of assets and vulnerable infrastructure take place (Buenos Aires, Mumbai, Croatian, Jakarta, Dhaka, Japanese cities, and Chinese floodplains). Most severe and susceptible to floods are low-lying polders behind an embanked river (as visible in Koshi basin), where flood levels may reach 5–10 meters over ground level. These situations occur in the river deltas of China, Japan, USA, Netherlands, India and Bangladesh (Van Alphen, Lodder, 2006).

Koshi River Basin

The River Koshi catchment area covers 6 climatic and geological belts varying in altitude from 95 m to more than 8,000 m. It comprises the Tibetan plateau, the Himalayas, mid-hill belt of the Himalaya, the Mahabharat Range, the Siwalik Hills, and the Terai region. The River Kosi or Koshi drains through the northern slopes of the Himalaya in the Tibet Region and southern slopes of the Nepal Himalaya before it finally enters the northern plains India in Bihar. Further river Koshi meets the River Ganga near Kursela, Katihar district in Bihar. The Koshi River basin comprises the borders of Tsangpo River basin in the north, the Ganga River basin in the south, the Mahananda River basin in the east, and the Gandaki River basin in the west. From the Chatra Gorge onwards, the River Koshi, also known as **Saptakoshi** because of its seven upper tributaries, which, includes the River Tamor, originates from the Kanchenjunga region in the east, River Arun and Sun Koshi from Autonomous Tibet region. Dudh Koshi, Bhote Koshi, Tamakoshi River, Likhu Khola and Indravati are the tributaries of Sun Koshi River from east to west. This Saptakoshi River drains into the northern region of Bihar from where it branches into distributaries before draining into the Ganga River near Kursela in Katihar district. The total basin area of mountain-fed Kosi River is around 84,739 sq. km and runs a total length of 730 km up to Baltara (Sinha and Friend, 1994; Gole and Chitale, 1966). The Tibetan area of the Koshi basin is characterized by high elevation with a flat plateau on the leeward side of the Himalaya as well as a huge number of glaciers or glacier lakes and it comprises around 22% drainage area of River Koshi (Bajracharya et al., 2007). Further, around 40% of the total drainage area of Kosi River basin lies in the

Nepal Himalaya and it is characterized by alpine and steep mountainous areas. The Kosi basin in Bihar plains, the alluvial part, comprises around 38% of the total drainage basin and characterized by low elevation and flat plains with the densely populated region. After reviewing 28 historical maps dating 1760 to 1960, it is evident that a slight eastward shifting has happened for a longer duration and it was haphazard and oscillating in nature.

After analysing the spatial distribution of rainfall, it is evident that the mid latitudinal basin receives the highest rainfall than a low and high latitudinal basin of Koshi River. Due to the leeward side of the location, the Tibetan basin receives the lowest rainfall, while the magnitude of rainfall decreases from the west to east of the Koshi basin.

Map-1, showing the location of the study area

All tributaries of the Kosi River originate from the high-altitude areas and, apart from rainfall, streamflow from glaciers; snow and permafrost contribute during the dry season (Singh et al., 1993; Bajracharya et al., 2007). The major drainage in the Tibetan region is marked by the tributaries of the Arun River flowing from the west as well from the east. In the Nepal Himalaya, the Kosi basin is drained by seven rivers: the Indrawati, Bhote Kosi, Tama Kosi, Dudh Kosi, Sun Kosi, Arun, and Tamor. The combined flow from these rivers reaches Tribeni through three major tributaries: the Sun Kosi from the west, the Tamor from the east, and Arun from the north (Sharma, 1977). At Koshi barrage of Birpur, a small town near Indo-Nepal frontier in Supaul district of Bihar, the flow of River Koshi is controlled. The Koshi River is embanked on both sides. Over the years, several breaks through the runoff in the embankment have been observed, which often leads to large floods. The Koshi River is characterised as an avulsive river due to its history of shifting its basin. On 18 August 2008, one most

recent and significant breach observed in the eastern embankment occurred at Kusaha in Nepal, 12 km upstream of the Birpur Kosi Barrage. This caused a major shift of the Kosi River by ~120 km eastward, and globally, it was one of the significant avulsions in a big river in recent years (Sinha, 2009a; Chakraborty et al., 2010; Sinha et al., 2014).

Data and Methods

Flood is one of the most significant natural hazards and people living in flood zone always face the event of flood during monsoon in India. The present study assesses the historical impacts of Koshi flood, particularly 'The Killed' and 'The Billed', in Northern Bihar. The aftermath of severe floods in the past has been assessed with the help of the secondary database. Lack of services, fragile living, and disadvantaged groups make people vulnerable to flood in the Koshi region of Bihar. The present study also tries to analyse the geographical problem of River Koshi in the northern plain of Bihar. The focus area comprises Madhubani, Darbhanga, Supaul, Saharsa, Khagaria, Madhepura, Araria, Katihar, Purnia and Bhagalpur districts of northern Bihar. The data related to damage to crops, damage to houses, damage to public utilities, loss of cattle life and loss of human life for various years has been collected from Disaster Management Department, Govt. of Bihar. The data of historical change of courses of Koshi river has been taken from the master plan for Flood and Sediment Management in Kosi River Basin (volume -I, part-I), 2016.

The study is completely based on a quantitative methodology. MS-Excel has been used to process and analyse the data. Various tables and figures have been created with MS-Excel. ArcGIS 10.3.1 has been used to draw the location Map of the study area as well as to show the spatial distribution of attributes.

Results and analysis

Theoretical Framework: Any such event, which leads to destruction and distress in a widespread area of life, is known as disaster. A disaster can be Natural (Earthquake, Flood, Cyclone etc.) as well as Human-induced (Fire, major explosions, Major transportation accidents, groundwater contamination etc.). Hazard is identified as such an event, which has the potential to destruction to property or life in a widespread area. Further, it can be also classified in Natural and Man-made hazards. The vulnerability can be defined as exposure or inability of the individuals, group, community, society, to deal with an event (Disaster) effectively (Roy, N. and Pandey, B.W., 2016.). Cutter (1996) described the vulnerability as a potential for loss due to an event. Asia-Pacific Disaster Report, (2012), mentioned that Disaster/Hazard risk can generally be described as the function of a specific hazard, physical exposure of elements at risk and human vulnerability. They are at times referred to "realized risk" or "disaster losses" (Peduzzi, 2012). By observing the associated components of risk as explained by UNDR0 (1979) in the notation,

$$[R = H * E * V]$$

Where: R = Risk (expected losses for a specific length of time, hazard type and intensity)

H = Hazard (frequency of occurrence, for a specific intensity)

E = Elements at risk (number of people or assets),

V = Vulnerability

Thus, Disaster management can be defined as the body of policy framework, institutional setup, administrative decisions and operational actions which refer to the different stages of a disaster. It can be classified into three different stages of Pre-disaster (comprises preparedness and mitigation), during a disaster (when disaster occur) and Post-disaster (Response and recovery capacity).

The present theoretical framework is based on existing pieces of literature, which emphasizes that vulnerability is a complex and multifaceted concept (Kelly, and Adger, 2000; Chambers, 1989; Ellis, 2008). Further, it can be measured by three fundamental components, such as exposure, susceptibility, and resilience. Exposure can be defined as the location of people or economic and social assets in hazard-prone areas subject to potential losses. They are also widely known as "elements at risk" (UNISDR, 2011b). "Resilience is "the ability of a system, community or society exposed to hazards to

resist, absorb, accommodate and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner, including through the preservation and restoration of its essential basic structures and functions” (UNISDR, 2011a). While there is no inclusive approach of measuring vulnerability, resilience and coping capacity physically, there are several methods available that try to understand these concepts and characterize them as usefully as possible (Birkmann et al., 2006). As far as ‘susceptibility’ is concerned, it can be referred to the pre-existing socio-economic conditions of societies or communities that increase their vulnerability to several external factors.

Figure-1, Disaster cycle

The components of hazard vulnerability about the timing of an event

The above figure demonstrates the cyclical interrelationships between key components (Exposure, Susceptibility, Resilience, and response & recovery) of disaster management. It also shows that each component can be classified about specific time phases, before or post of a hazard event. As evident in the figure and with the help of existing literature, we can derive that ‘exposure’ and ‘susceptibility’ are characterized as before the hazard event. While, ‘resilience’, being linked to managing and response capacity, is characterized by the system’s capacity to absorb and recover from the impacts, i.e., post hazard event.

The problem of Koshi River:

Problems of the Koshi river basin may be categorized as:

a. **The problem of river shifting:** As Koshi is very volatile in terms of its course. Historically, it is evident from the table; River Koshi has changed its course significantly from north-eastern Bihar to the north-western region of Bihar.

Table-1. Shifting of Koshi River Channel (1736-1950)

Year	Period of movement (in years)	Distance moved (in Kms)	Avg rate of movement (in km/year)
1736-1770	34	10.8	0.318
1770-1823	53	9.3	0.175
1823-1856	33	6.1	0.185
1856-1883	27	12.9	0.478
1883-1907	24	18.5	0.771
1907-1922	15	10.9	0.727
1922-1933	11	29	2.636
1933-1950	17	17.7	1.041
Total	214	115.2	0.538 (Mean)

(Source: History of Kosi Project—Vol1, WRD, GoB)

Koshi River has moved around 115 km during the phase of 1736 to 1950. During this 214 year, it has shifted its course 115.2 km in western direction at an average rate of 0.538 km per annum. It means it has a very broad riparian region, which makes this focus area more vulnerable to flood.

b. The problem of heavy sediment load: As, Koshi river has its origin in the higher altitude of Tibet, where, with its extensive erosional work, it erodes high sediments and transport them through the Nepal Himalayan region and finally, deposit them in the middle and lower course of the river in northern Bihar.

c.

Table-2. Measurements of Accumulated Suspended Sediment at Barakshetra in Various Years

Year	Total Sediment Volume (in MCM)	Year	Total Sediment Volume (in MCM)
1948	103.61	1965	57.36
1949	151.96	1966	92.63
1950	93.25	1967	61.92
1951	102.75	1968	172.35
1952	98.8	1969	95.22
1953	81.53	1970	194.03
1954	283.45	1971	92.39
1955	69.32	1972	63.15
1956	68.7	1973	73.46
1957	59.7	1974	82.77
1958	105.22	1975	65.38
1959	87.45	1976	77.78
1960	72.15	1977	55.88
1961	59.08	1978	79.44
1962	83.14	1979	49.32
1963	72.9	1980	161.26
1964	82.52		
		Mean	94.95

(Source: History of Kosi Project—Vol1, WRD, GoB)

As a huge amount of sediment has been deposited in northern plains of Bihar, the riverbed of Koshi increase significantly every year. This contributes to making this region prone to flood. As riverbed rises in Koshi, the natural longitudinal course of the river is disturbed and the river starts searching for a lateral path (either left or right). By this process, the Koshi River breaches the embankments on either side of the river. The breach of embankments causes floods. In the table, it is evident that year 1954 has recorded the highest volume of sediment deposit (283.45 MCM) in a single year from 1948 to 1980. On the other hand, 1979 has recorded the lowest volume of sediment (49.32 MCM) during the same period. This phase has recorded an average of 94.95 MCM per annum from 1948 to 1980. This issue of deposition of sediment in northern plains of Bihar, make them prone to flood.

d. The problem of flooding: The Lower catchment area of Koshi River system is affected severely by floods each year. As the river with its tributaries such as Kamla Balan, Bagmati and Adhawara group emerge from the hills and enter into plains of Nepal Terai and Bihar, the velocity of flow of rivers dropped significantly. This reduces the silt carrying capacity of the river by which, silts

are deposited in riverbed. This increase the riverbed of the river in this region, which further makes this region vulnerable to flood.

e. Above mentioned issues further contributes to waterlogging and congestion in drainage in-focus area.

Impact of Koshi flood in the Study Area

In a developing like India, Floods possess a bigger hazard to human life, assets as well as health and well-being in compare to a developed nation. In general two-thirds of deaths directly related to flood events are caused by drowning and one-third by physical trauma, heart attack and electrocution (Fitzgerald et al., 2010). The most susceptible members of the society or community are the younger and elderly ones.

Flood is a Spatio-temporal phenomenon. It is evident that the larger the area and longer the duration of the flood, will impact greater in terms of economic loss or loss of lives. It has both a direct and indirect impact on the region. Drowning is the major factor in the loss of life during flooding. Apart from drowning, death is experienced due to death due to diarrhoea, dysentery, typhoid and cholera as well. Snake bites also are a major hazard during the flood. As measures of flood prevention are increasing with time, the number of death continues to decline. The impacts of flooding in northern Bihar are severe in both rural areas in particular and urban areas, in general. Death due to flood, constitute cattle lives as well.

Figure-2. Showing Loss of Human Lives During 1968 – 2017.

Source: Cumulative Form IX, Disaster Management Department, Government of Bihar.

During 2008 – 2017, the highest number of death of human lives (1424 deaths) has been recorded. The flood of 2008 constitutes more than one-third (550) of total death alone, while flood events of 2008, 2016 and 2017 comprise more than four-fifth (1217) of total death during 2008-2017. While the phase of 1968-1977 recorded the least death (51).

Figure-3. Showing Loss of Cattle Lives During 1968 – 2017

Source: Cumulative Form IX, Disaster Management Department, Government of Bihar

As far as cattle lives are concerned, the highest number of death (32346) has been registered again during 2008-2017 phase. This phase comprises 3 major events of 2008, 2016 and 2017. While during 1988-1997, least death (274) of cattle lives recorded.

Source: Cumulative Form IX, Disaster Management Department, Government of Bihar

When we analyse the spatial distribution of loss of lives in the study area of Koshi River basin in northern Bihar, we find that during 2008-2017, Madhepura, Supaul, Darbhanga and Araria districts

has been severely (more than 200 deaths) impacted by flood events in the past. Purnea, Katihar, and Saharsa can be categorized into moderately (100-200 deaths) affected districts. Madhubani, Bhagalpur and Khagaria come under least (less than 100 deaths) affected regions.

In Northern Bihar, Flood in lower Koshi basin hamper usual activities and during and after devastating floods, which further increase the vulnerability of the community and society. The 2008 Koshi flood has affected much of northern Bihar in all aspects, whether it is the loss of lives or loss of assets, properties and crops. It is evident from the study that, during 1968-1987 damage to crops in northern Bihar comprises significant share than damage to household and damage to public property. With the help of steps taken by the government on a regional scale the share of crop damage falls significantly in subsequent years.

Figure-4. Showing Damage to assets and properties during 1968-2017

Source: Cumulative Form IX, Disaster Management Department, Government of Bihar

During 1968-1977, damage to crops valued ~ INR 286,497.24 lac (at 2020 constant price), which was around 90% of the total share, while during 2008-2017 the share of crop damage came down to around 25%. Due to urbanization processes and infrastructural development in past decades, the share of damage to public property and household increased rapidly. During 2008-2017, damage to household and public property comprises around three fourth (~INR 284134 lac, at 2020 constant price) of total damage (~378913.47, at 2020 constant price).

Figure-5. Showing damage to assets in various districts during 2008-2017

Source: Cumulative Form IX, Disaster Management Department, Government of Bihar

During a flood in rural areas, houses with Coconut leaf Walls, Mud Walls, and Tin Walls make people and their assets more vulnerable. Thus, after a flood event, a large number of people becomes homeless for months during the flood. During 2008-2017, seven major flood events have been observed, when human fatality was more than 100 in lower Koshi basin of Bihar. In this phase, household damage comprises more than 50% of the total property damage. Katihar (~INR76100 lac), Madhepura (~INR48370 lac) and Supaul (~INR35777 lac) suffered from huge damage during 2008-2017.

CONCLUSION

Flood in lower Koshi basin of Bihar is a frequent and recurrent phenomenon. As most of the settlement in this region is rural in nature, floods harm society and communities. Apart from the loss of lives of human and cattle, it also damages the crops, households, public properties and infrastructures. Thus it impacts the socio-economic condition of the region, which leaves humanity in distress. Floods in Koshi basin of northern Bihar is recurrent and unavoidable, hence there is need of proper and systematic preparedness to reduce the impact of floods in this region. Though, the government of Bihar as well as the central government trying to reduce the every year damage in the region, but their steps and policies are seldom effective. There is a need for an inclusive approach to reduce the risk of flood in the region. Along with governmental and non-governmental policies, indigenous practices, community participation, traditional knowledge should also be integrated to reduce the vulnerability and socio-economic implication of flood in lower Koshi basin of northern Bihar.

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